

Syllabus

«Quantum Computing Basis»

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Expected learning outcomes.

As a result of studying the discipline, the student.

must know:

- Description of the state and dynamics of a system in quantum mechanics, quantum-mechanical measurements.
- Qubits - as a basic concept of quantum informatics.
- Formation of the space of many qubits (tensor product).
- Quantum logic elements, quantum networks.
- Basic quantum algorithms.
- Features of programming languages for quantum computing.

must be able to:

Purpose:

- Understand what a quantum computer is and what they are good at
- Learning the fundamentals of how to code in Python
- Understand quantum superposition and how it relates to quantum measurement.
- Program a quantum algorithm in Python using IBM Qiskit.

The content of the discipline

Module one. Introduction

Module 2. Concepts and fundamentals of quantum computing

Module 3. Hardware and physical realizations of qubits and quantum computers

Module 4. Quantum circuits, algorithms, and error correction

Module 5. Applied aspects of quantum computing.

Evaluation criteria of laboratory works / practices / individual works / reports / projects.

90–100 points (PASSED, grade A) – a student with high quality independently performed the entire scope of work, answered all questions related to the work performed, and made additional calculations, for example, using the neural network methods the teacher offered.

- Describe the state and dynamics of quantum-mechanical systems, and determine the state of the system after measurement.
- from the space of many qubits.
- apply the action of one- and two-qubit quantum elements.
- use of entangled and superposition states to solve problems of information

Prerequisites

"Physics," "Higher mathematics," "Fundamentals of programming," "Probability Theory and math statistics"

Consequences

The knowledge gained in the discipline can be applied to the disciplines or areas of Computer Engineering, as well as to pre-diploma practice and the preparation of qualification work.

Evaluation

For the semester: 70/60 points

For assessment: 30/40 points

Types of works

Lectures & Laboratory Practicum

Technical support

1. Maple - a computer mathematics system from Maplesoft.
<https://maplesoft.com/index.html>
2. Online Bloch sphere simulator (Bloch sphere simulator.
<https://bloch.kherb.io/>)
3. Spin Laboratory (online simulator, Spins Laboratory
<https://physics.weber.edu/schroeder/software/Spins.html>)

The teacher has no complaints about the software implementation and performance requirements.

82–89 points (PASSED, grade B) – a student with sufficient quality independently completed all tasks. Still, in the process, he made some mistakes, which he corrected after the teacher pointed them out. He answers some questions with a slight error. The additional calculations offered by the teacher are somewhat complex. Not all work requirements are met.

75–81 points (PASSED, grade C) – a student of average quality independently completed all tasks but did not meet all the requirements for implementation. He answers the question with a slight error. The additional calculations offered by the teacher, for example, using neural network methods, make insignificant errors. Not all requirements for the design of the work are met.

67–74 points (PASSED, grade D) – a student performed all the work independently, but the quality of implementation is insufficient (errors in calculations, not all work requirements are met).

60–66 points (PASSED, grade E) – a student did not perform the entire amount of work. The answers to the questions about the work are not entirely clear. There are errors in the answers.

Less than 60 points (FAILED, grade F, FX) – a student performed work with gross errors. He has problems with calculations by certain methods, does not know the theoretical material, and the software implementation does not meet the requirements.

4. Online quantum circuit simulator (Quirk, <https://algassert.com/quirk>)

Note: Maple is a licensed product; online simulators are free.